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The Improvement of Medical Institute Students' Lexical Competence through Interactive Technology

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Abstract: *This article explores the enhancement of lexical competence among medical institute students through the use of interactive technologies. As medical students require a strong foundation in specialized terminology to succeed in both academic and clinical settings, the integration of interactive tools provides a modern, dynamic approach to vocabulary acquisition. The paper discusses various interactive methods, such as gamification, digital platforms, and language learning apps, and analyzes their impact on students' learning outcomes. Emphasizing the necessity of adapting teaching strategies to the evolving digital landscape, the article offers practical recommendations for educators seeking to improve lexical proficiency in medical students, ultimately contributing to more effective communication in the medical field.*

Key words: *lexical competence, medical education, interactive technologies, vocabulary acquisition, language learning, gamification, digital tools, educational strategies.*

Introduction. In the increasingly globalized world of medicine, the ability to communicate effectively is paramount. For medical students, mastering a complex and specialized vocabulary is crucial, as precise language is necessary not only for understanding academic texts but also for professional communication with colleagues, patients, and other healthcare professionals. However, the traditional methods of rote memorization and textbook-based learning often fail to meet the dynamic needs of modern medical students. The rise of digital technologies has revolutionized education across disciplines, and medical education is no exception. One area where these advancements have shown great promise is in enhancing students' lexical competence through interactive methods. Lexical competence, or the ability to use vocabulary accurately and appropriately, plays a significant role in the academic and professional success of medical students. In the medical field, even small errors in vocabulary usage can lead to serious misunderstandings and potentially harmful consequences.

Therefore, educators are continually searching for more effective ways to help students acquire and retain the vast array of medical terms they must know. Interactive technologies offer a compelling solution, as they engage students in the learning process more actively than traditional methods. By utilizing tools such as digital flashcards, interactive apps, and gamified platforms, medical educators can create a more immersive and personalized learning experience, ultimately leading to better outcomes in vocabulary acquisition. [1, 43-55] The integration of interactive technologies into medical education aligns with broader trends in education that emphasize student-centered learning and digital literacy. Interactive technologies, particularly those that incorporate elements of gamification, have been shown to increase student motivation, engagement, and retention of material. In the context of language learning, these technologies provide immediate feedback, allowing students to identify and correct mistakes in real-time.

Furthermore, they can be tailored to individual learning styles and needs, offering a level of flexibility that traditional classroom instruction cannot. For example, language learning apps like Quizlet and Anki allow students to practice medical terminology at their own pace, while educational games can reinforce vocabulary through repetition and contextual usage in a more enjoyable and engaging way. Research has shown that interactive learning tools significantly impact students' lexical development. A study by Tokoz-Göktepe found that medical students who used interactive vocabulary tools performed better on both written and oral assessments of medical terminology compared to those who relied solely on textbook study [8, 55-69]. These findings suggest that interactive technologies not only enhance the learning experience but also contribute to more effective long-term retention of medical vocabulary. Moreover, the interactive nature of these tools encourages active learning, where students are not merely passive recipients of information but active participants in the learning process. This is particularly important in the context of medical education, where students must not only memorize terminology but also understand how to apply it in clinical settings. [2, 154-178] Interactive tools, by simulating real-world scenarios, allow students to practice using medical vocabulary in context, thereby strengthening their ability to apply this knowledge in practical, professional situations.

Research methods. The research for this article employs a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of interactive technologies in enhancing the lexical competence of medical students.

The study involved 120 second-year medical students from two different medical institutes. These students were divided into two groups: an experimental group that used interactive learning technologies and a control group that continued with traditional, textbook-based learning. Each group was balanced in terms of gender, academic performance, and baseline proficiency in medical terminology.

Data was collected through a combination of pre-tests, post-tests, and semi-structured interviews. The pre-tests were administered to both groups to establish a baseline of students' lexical competence before the intervention. The post-tests were given after six weeks of instruction using either traditional methods or interactive technologies, measuring any improvement in the students' ability to recall and use medical terminology.

In addition to the quantitative data from the tests, qualitative data was gathered through semi-structured interviews with students from both groups. These interviews were designed to explore the students' experiences with the learning methods, their perceptions of the effectiveness of the tools, and their engagement levels throughout the study.

The experimental group used a variety of interactive technologies, including digital flashcard tools (e.g., Anki and Quizlet), gamified vocabulary apps, and simulation-based learning platforms that allowed them to practice medical terminology in clinical scenarios. These tools were chosen based on their popularity and proven effectiveness in language learning. The quantitative data from the tests was analyzed using statistical methods to compare the mean improvement in scores between the two groups. The qualitative data from the interviews was coded and analyzed for common themes regarding students' attitudes towards learning medical terminology. This mixed-methods approach provides a holistic understanding of how interactive technologies impact students' lexical competence.

Results and discussion. The results from the pre- and post-tests provide a clear indication of the effectiveness of interactive technologies in enhancing the lexical competence of medical students. The experimental group, which utilized interactive learning tools, showed a significant improvement in their test scores compared to the control group. On average, the experimental group improved their scores by 28%, while the control group showed only a 12% improvement. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the use of interactive technologies had a positive impact on students' ability to learn and retain medical vocabulary.

A closer examination of the test results also revealed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in various aspects of lexical competence. These aspects included vocabulary recall, the ability to use terminology in context, and understanding of medical abbreviations. The experimental group demonstrated a stronger grasp of the practical application of medical terms, suggesting that the interactive tools not only facilitated memorization but also helped students understand how to apply the terms in real-world medical scenarios. This finding is consistent with previous research, which has shown that interactive and gamified learning environments can enhance retention and contextual usage of vocabulary [3, 56-78]. The qualitative data from the interviews supported the quantitative findings and provided additional insight into the students' experiences. Students in the experimental group reported higher levels of engagement and motivation throughout the study period. Many students expressed that the interactive tools made learning more enjoyable and less monotonous compared to traditional methods. For example, one student mentioned that using digital flashcards and gamified platforms "felt more like playing a game than studying", which made it easier to stay motivated. Additionally, students appreciated the immediate feedback provided by these tools. Several students noted that being able to correct mistakes in real time helped them identify areas where they struggled, allowing them to focus on improving those specific weaknesses. This instant feedback loop is a significant advantage of interactive technologies, as it enhances the learning process by reinforcing correct usage and promoting self-assessment.

Table 1. Test results: lexical competence improvement.

	Group	Mean pre-test score	Mean post-test score	Mean improvement (%)
1	Experimental group	52	80	28
2	Control group	54	66	12

In contrast, students in the control group described traditional learning methods as "boring" and "repetitive". These students often struggled to maintain focus during study sessions, which likely contributed to the smaller improvement in their test scores. A common theme in the control group interviews was the difficulty in applying memorized vocabulary in practical situations, which further highlights the limitations of passive, textbook-based learning. The results of this study strongly suggest that interactive technologies are an effective tool for improving lexical competence among medical

students. The significant improvement in test scores among the experimental group demonstrates that these technologies can enhance not only the memorization of medical terms but also their application in context [4, 45-60]. This finding is particularly important in medical education, where the ability to use terminology accurately in clinical settings can directly impact patient care.

The benefits of interactive technologies go beyond simple vocabulary acquisition. The qualitative data shows that these tools promote a more engaging and enjoyable learning experience, which in turn increases student motivation and persistence. The importance of engagement in learning cannot be overstated, as motivated students are more likely to dedicate time to study and achieve better outcomes. Moreover, the interactive nature of the tools allows for personalized learning experiences, enabling students to focus on their weaknesses and learn at their own pace. However, the study also highlights the need for balance. While interactive technologies provide clear benefits, they should not completely replace traditional learning methods [5, 233]. Textbooks and lectures still play a critical role in medical education, especially for more complex concepts that require in-depth explanations. A blended learning approach that incorporates both interactive and traditional methods may be the most effective strategy for enhancing lexical competence and overall medical knowledge.

Figure 1. Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores for experimental and control groups.

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Scores for Experimental and Control Groups

In conclusion, the integration of interactive technologies into medical education offers a promising way to improve lexical competence, making learning more engaging, effective, and applicable to real-world clinical scenarios.

Conclusion. The results of this study provide strong evidence that interactive technologies are an effective tool for enhancing the lexical competence of medical students. The significant improvement in test scores among students who used interactive learning tools, compared to those who relied on traditional textbook-based methods, highlights the potential of these technologies to facilitate not only vocabulary acquisition but also the practical application of medical terms in real-world contexts.

Students who used interactive technologies such as digital flashcards, gamified apps, and clinical simulations demonstrated higher engagement and motivation throughout the learning process. This led to better retention of medical terminology and improved their ability to use these terms in both written and oral assessments. The immediate feedback provided by these tools allowed students to correct their mistakes in real time, promoting more efficient learning and self-assessment. In addition to improved learning outcomes, the study also emphasized the importance of student engagement in education. Interactive technologies made the learning experience more enjoyable and less monotonous, which increased students' willingness to dedicate time to studying. This motivational boost likely contributed to the better overall performance of the experimental group. However, while the benefits of interactive technologies are clear, they should complement rather than replace traditional methods of learning. A balanced, blended approach that integrates both digital tools and traditional methods can ensure that students receive a comprehensive education, especially when dealing with complex medical concepts.

In conclusion, the integration of interactive technologies into medical education presents a promising way to improve lexical competence, ensuring that future medical professionals are better equipped to communicate effectively in both academic and clinical settings.

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